

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetic parameters of submergence tolerance in some rainfed lowland rices of Bangladesh

M. S. Pathan and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

We used five rainfed lowland rice cultivars—one resistant, two moderately resistant, and two susceptible to submergence (FR13A, Dudmona, Kumragoir, Nizersail, and BR5)—to make one-way diallel crosses without reciprocal in 1983-85.

The ratios of submergence tolerance showed that dominant components were highly significant (see table), indicating the important role of additive as well as dominant genes. The dominance ratio $(H_1/D)^{1/2}$ of 0.55 (partial dominance) was also supported by graphic analysis (see figure). The proportion of the gene in the parents $(H_2/4H_1)$ showed some degree of gene asymmetry in favor of recessive alleles, as evidenced by the negative sign of F. The dominant and

Genetic parameters of submergence tolerance and their ratios. Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1983-85.

Genetic parameter	Estimates ^a
D (additive)	4.031** ± 0.038
H ₁ (dominance)	1.229** ± 0.278
H ₂ (dominance)	1.291** ± 0.229
h ² (dominance)	1.356** ± 0.104
F (additive, dominance, and gene asymmetry)	-1.444 ± 0.238
E (environment)	0.042 ± 0.006
$(H_1/D)^{1/2}$ (average dominance)	0.552
$(H_2/4H_1)$ (gene asymmetry)	0.263
h^2/H_2 (number of gene blocks)	1.050
$\frac{1}{2}D + \frac{1}{2}H_1 - \frac{1}{2}H_2 - \frac{1}{2}F$	0.880
$(\frac{1}{2}D + \frac{1}{2}H_1 - \frac{1}{2}H_2 - \frac{1}{2}F) + E$ (narrow-sense heritability)	

^a**Significant at the 0.01 level.

Covariance (Wr)/variance (Vr) regression of submergence tolerance. Parents are 1) BR5, 2) Nizersail, 3) Kumragoir, 4) Dudmona, and 5) FR13A.

recessive genes were in unequal proportions in the parent (ratio 0.51).

The ratio of h^2/H_2 was 1.05, suggesting involvement of at least 1 major gene or a group of genes having partial dominance. The Vr, Wr graph analysis shows that the parents FR13A possesses the most resistant alleles and BR5 and Nizersail possess susceptible alleles for submergence tolerance. The high narrow-sense heritability (0.88) showed the importance of additive gene action in submergence tolerance. □

Combining ability of upland rice progenitors

E. P. Guimarães, EMBRAPA/Centro Nacional de Pesquisa de Arroz e Feijão (CNPAP), Caixa Postal 179, 74000 Goiânia, GO, Brazil

In the 1987-88 season, 140 F₂ upland rice populations were evaluated in the CNPAF breeding program; 79 were discarded due to neck blast (Bl) susceptibility.

To study combining ability, the progenitors crossed at least 7 times were chosen from the total 63 used to make

Combining ability of upland rice progenitors. CNPAF, Brazil, 1987-88.

Progenitor	Populations (no.)		Populations (no.) with phenotypic variability			Neck Bl	
	Selected	Discarded	High	Medium	Low	Average	Range
Araguaia	8	1	1	8	0	4.2	3.0-6.0
A8-204-1	10	0	3	6	1	4.8	4.0-6.0
Cuiabana	8	0	1	6	1	4.1	3.0-5.0
IRAT216	10	0	3	6	1	5.1	3.0-6.0
Cabapu	7	2	4	3	2	5.2	3.0-7.0
CNA4640	7	2	2	5	2	5.3	3.0-8.0
CNA5180	7	2	4	3	2	5.2	3.0-7.0
IAC82-276	6	1	0	1	6	5.0	3.0-7.0
CNA4157	2	5	3	1	3	6.9	6.0-8.0
Mut. Makouta 41-1-3	3	4	1	0	6	5.3	4.0-7.0
TOm 1-3	2	5	7	0	0	6.7	5.0-8.0
Apura (indica group)	1	10	11	0	0	6.9	6.0-8.0

the F₂ populations. The parameters evaluated were a) number of populations selected, b) phenotypic variability, and c) neck B1 score.

Good combining progenitors had the majority of the crosses selected, showed medium to high phenotypic variability, and had neck B1 scores not above 6 in

any cross. Araguaia, A8-204-1, Cuiabana, and IRAT216 were included in this group (see table). A second group with a lower combining ability included Cabacçu, CNA4640, CNA5180, and IAC82-276. CNA4157, Mut. Makouta 41-1-3, and TOM 1-3 showed poor combining ability.

A few single cross progenitors from the indica group were combined with japonicas, but the preliminary data did not show good results. The crosses produced very high phenotypic variability and susceptibility to neck B1. □

Breeding methods

Segregation of aroma character in F₂ hybrid rice grain

Bai Delang and Zhou Kunlu, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center (HHRRC), Changsha, Hunan, China

F₂ seeds from five F₁ rice hybrids derived from aromatic CMS line Xiang xiang IIA and five restorer varieties were tasted to identify aroma.

Segregation was 15 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic grain (see table), indicating

Segregation of aroma in F₂ seeds borne by hybrids. HHRRC, Hunan, China.

Hybrid	Scented seed (no.)	Nonscented seed (no.)	χ^2	1 = 15	P
Xiang Xiang II A/PH137	67	933	0.27		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/26 Zhai Zao	59	941	0.15		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/Ming Tei 63	65	935	0.07		>0.75
Xiang Xiang II A/Ce 64	58	942	0.34		>0.50
Xiang Xiang II A/F 200	60	940	0.07		>0.75

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{k(UQ - EI - \frac{1}{2})^2}{E}$$

that aroma in the CMS line was controlled by 2 recessive genes. Absence of either gene resulted in nonaromatic grains.

The F₁ hybrids do not have an aroma during growth, but seed processing releases their aroma. □

Performance of two rice hybrids under upland conditions with and without fertilizer

O. Suherman and I. T. Corpuz, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Experimental rice hybrids V41A/ IR54 and V41A/Sadang, developed for irrigated conditions in Indonesia, were compared with maintainer V20B, male parent Sadang, conventional upland varieties Tondano and C22, very short-duration rainfed lowland variety IR58, and promising upland variety IR9575 Sel. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Fertilizer treatments were the mainplots and rice entries the subplots.

The trial was conducted 19 Nov 1987-20 Mar 1988 at Bontobili experimental farm, under agroclimatic zone B₂ (7-9 mo with monthly rainfall more than 200

Performance of rice hybrids and conventional varieties under upland conditions, with and without fertilizer. Bontobili, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1987-88 wet season.

Entry	Plant height at harvest (cm)		Panicles (no./m ²)		Filled grains (no./panicle)		Grain yield (t/ha at 14% moisture)	
	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	Without fertilizer
V41A/IR54	93.0	82.0	263	205	83	72	2.4	1.9
V41A/Sadang	98.7	81.7	263	223	87	76	1.8	1.7
V20B	73.1	72.3	367	196	74	72	2.1	1.6
Sadang	102.3	82.7	291	204	79	79	2.2	1.7
Tondano	122.7	106.7	259	177	84	75	2.7	2.0
IR58	73.7	67.0	373	185	78	51	2.2	1.8
C22	145.0	118.3	252	191	95	93	2.4	1.9
IR9575 Sel	129.3	101.7	253	179	124	113	3.4	2.2
Mean	104.8	89.1	280	195	88	79	2.39	1.86
CV (%)								
(a)		7		16		12		19
(b)		8		13		11		16
LSD (5%)								
(a)		7.9		48		ns		0.5
(b)		9.1		37		11		0.4

mm, and 2-3 mo with monthly rainfall less than 100 mm). Soil is Ultic Haplustalf, fine mixed, isohyperthermic. It has clay loam texture; pH 5.7;

available P (Bray₁) 39 ppm; 0.6, 8.8, 2.5, 0.2, and 0.3 meq exchangeable K, Ca, Mg, Na, and Al/ 100 g soils, respectively; and 0.1% total N and 1.8% organic